

Forecasting Solar Flares with Machine Learning Algorithms

André Leon S. Gravohl¹

¹Faculdade de Tecnologia – Universidade Estadual de Campinas

ABSTRACT

Space Weather refers to the phenomena occurring on the Sun that affect Earth's magnetosphere and ionosphere. These phenomena - among them solar flares - influence the performance and reliability of technological systems on Earth or in its near orbit. Since 2015, the HighPIDS research group has been dedicated to research on solar flares forecasting. To develop solar flares forecasting, the HighPIDS group researches strategies that use machine learning and deep learning algorithms, combined with methodologies for attribute selection, optimizing hyperparameters selection, unbalanced data handling, and finding a good relationship between forecast horizons and accuracy. The proofs-of-concept developed so far obtained accuracies between 70% and 85%, with forecast horizons from 24 to 72 hours in advance for high-intensity solar flares ($\geq C$ class). The proof-of-concept is available on the web as a service called Guaraci. This paper summarizes of the results achieved by the HighPIDS research group so far and some prospects for future research in solar flare forecasting.

Keywords: Solar Flares, Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Forecasting.

INTRODUCTION

The Sun has an active atmosphere and presents several phenomena that directly affect the planets around it, particularly the Earth. These phenomena can cause damage to technologies used on and near the Earth (orbiting the planet), including aerospace technologies, satellites, oil and gas industries, electrical and communication systems. Depending on the magnitude of these phenomena, their occurrence can lead to economic and commercial losses [1]. These phenomena that occur on the Sun and have repercussions on Earth are called Space Weather.

Solar flares are one of the most significant phenomena produced by the Sun. They are sudden releases of large amounts of radiation and particles that can affect the Earth's atmosphere within hours or days after they occur. Solar flares release x-rays between 1 and 8 Ångström (Å) measured in W/m^2 , and we classify them on a scaleranging from A (less intense), B, C, M, and X (most intense). Each flare class has a peak flux

ten times higher than the preceding class. Besides, except on the X class, in each other classes, there is a range on a linear scale from 1 to 9, representing the solar flare's intensity.

The sunspots are the physical phenomenon precursor to solar flares [2]. In other words, solar flares arise from sunspots of different polarities when they approach each other. These spots appear as dark, temporary, relatively cooler areas on the Sun's surface where the local magnetic field is strong. These spots appear on the solar photosphere in different colors depending on the solar disc wavelength image. As they coalesce, the sunspots form the so-called active regions (AR), which in turn have a strong magnetic field capable of producing solar flares.

When sunspots of different polarities approach each other, a magnetic arc forms between them. When the magnetic arc breaks, a solar flare occurs. In addition to the brightness caused by the flare, the event releases radiation, and coronal mass ejection (CME) can also occur depending on the event's intensity.

Research in the area of machine learning applied to solar flare forecasting

There is much research going on in the area of solar flare forecasting. In this area, some research uses machine learning algorithms to predict solar flares. However, in many cases, we use some attributes - data on various solar activity measurements - to train and validate the artificial neural networks used to forecast solar flares' occurrence.

Much of the work considers the occurrence and class of previous events, the magnetic classification of sunspots, the sunspots area of the spots, and other relevant attributes. The works from the HighPIDS group are some examples of research in the area of space weather forecasting [3, 4, 5, 6, 7].

Another work [8] - also from the HighPIDS group -- focuses on analyzing solar images at different wavelengths. Each wavelength can reveal a different feature of the phenomena associated with solar flares and CMEs, as indicated by [9]. In this case, the research seeks to analyze Sun images at different wavelengths to extract visual features of the active regions and, from there, to infer the probability of the occurrence of solar flares. To date, many works focus on analyzing magnetograms in the Helioseismic and Magnetic Imager (HMI) format. Besides, much of this work uses convolutional neural networks for Deep Learning.

METHODOLOGY

We divide the methodology common to HighPIDS research in the solar flare forecasting area into steps that include building and curating the datasets, analyzing algorithms for machine learning and deep learning applied to solar flare forecasting, and evaluating results based on standard metrics.

The methodology starts with a survey of the relevant attributes to characterize solar flares. Regarding the attributes for solar flares, previous works [3, 4, 5,] surveyed these attributes that rely on solar cycles 23 and

24. The data came mainly from the Space Weather Prediction Center of the US National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration. After we have gathered the necessary data, we perform the following steps.

- Data partitioning: segmentation of data into training, validation, and test sets.
- Model selection: choosing the model that minimizes the training error by combining several machine learning algorithms.
- Attribute Selection: Choosing the attributes that best contribute to an accurate model.
- Hyperparameter Optimization: Tuning the parameters that control the learning process.
- Resampling of the data: if necessary, we treat the unbalance of the dataset and generate new samples.

To evaluate the performance of the entire system and the combination of the algorithms in the various steps, we use the metrics that consider correctly predicted positive samples (true positive - TP); correctly predicted negative samples (true negative - TN); incorrectly predicted positive samples (false positives FP); and incorrectly predicted negative samples (false negatives - FN). Using those variables, we calculate the following metrics.

- Precision or Positive Predictive Value: $PPV = \frac{TP}{TP+FP}$
- Negative Predictive Value: $NPV = \frac{TN}{TN+FN}$
- Accuracy: $ACC = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+FN+FP+TN}$
- True Positive Rate: $TPR = \frac{TP}{TP+FN}$
- True Negative Rate: $TNR = \frac{TN}{TN+FP}$
- F_1 -score: $F_1 = 2 \times \frac{PPV \times TPR}{PPV + TPR}$
- True Skill Statistics: $TSS = TPR + TNR - 1$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As a result of applying the proposed methodology, we developed a framework capable of evaluating the various algorithms used in each step. Then, based on the results of applying the specific algorithms for each step in the methodology, the framework indicates the best algorithm, according to the metrics.

The user is free to choose any combination of algorithms. However, the results showed that the combination proposed by the framework produces fairly consistent results.

We must emphasize that we did not explore all possible combinations of algorithms. The reason for such a choice is because, at each step, we can decide on the best algorithm at that point and abandon exploring combinations that gave good results, to the detriment of better results.

To consolidate these studies, we implemented the Guaraci¹ software, available on the web. Guaraci automatically searches for new data on solar flares and, based on the prediction algorithms, issues the probabilities of high-intensity flares ($\geq C$ class) for the next 24h, 48h, and 72h.

CONCLUSIONS

The research of the HighPIDS group is still in progress. Although the results are entirely satisfactory, especially when compared to the state-of-the-art, there is still a long way to go. For example, the Guaraci software can predict a solar flare, but it cannot yet tell which active region the flare will occur.

In this sense, the HighPIDS research group intends to seek new methods that, using raw data and deep learning image analysis, can more accurately answer when and at which point on the solar disk solar flares will occur.

REFERENCES

- [1] National Research Council, 2009, Severe Space Weather Events - Understanding Societal and Economic Impact, The National Academic Press, Washington, DC, doi 10.17226/12643, isbn 978-0-309-17762-7.
- [2] Li, R. & Zhu, J., 2013, "Solar flare forecasting based on sequential sunspot data", Research in Astronomy and Astrophysics, v13,n9,pp 1118-1126, doi 10.1088/1674-4527/13/9/010.
- [3] Ribeiro, F., & Gradvohl, A.L.S., 2021, "Machine learning techniques applied to solar flares forecasting", Astronomy and Computing, v35, pp 100468, doi 10.1016/j.ascom.2021.100468, issn 2213-1337.
- [4] Cinto, T., Gradvohl, A.L.S, Coelho, G.P. & da Silva, A.E.A., 2020, "A Framework for Designing and Evaluating Solar Flare Forecasting Systems",MNRAS, v5, pp 3332-3349, doi 10.1093/mnras/staa1257, issn 0035-8711, 1365-2966.
- [5] Cinto, T., Gradvohl, A.L.S, Coelho, G.P. & da Silva, A.E.A., 2020, "Solar Flares Forecasting Using Time Series and Extreme Gradient Boosting Ensembles", Solar Physics, v7, pp 93, doi 10.1007/s11207-020-01661-9, issn 0038-0938, 1573-093X.

¹ <https://highpids.ft.unicamp.br/guaraci>

- [6] Bueno, M.C., Coelho, G.P., da Silva A.E.A., Gradvohl, A.L.S, Sampaio, A.EL., 2018, "Evaluating the Impact of Pre-clustering and Class Imbalance on Solar Flare Forecasting", XV Encontro Nacional de Inteligência Artificial e Computacional, pub. SBC, São Paulo, PP 486-496, doi 10.5281/zenodo.1470483.
- [7] Caldana, I., da Silva, A.E.A., Coelho, G.P., Gradvohl, A.L.S., 2017, "Using X-Ray Flux Time Series for Solar Explosion Forecasting", 2017 Brazilian Conference on Intelligent Systems (BRACIS), pub IEEE, Uberlândia, pp 204-209, doi 10.1109/BRACIS.2017.31, isbn 978-1-5386-2407-4.
- [8] Oliveira, L.S.O., Gradvohl, A.L.S., 2020, "Automatic analysis of magnetograms for identification and classification of active regions using Deep Learning", Revista Brasileira de Computação Aplicada, UPF Editora, v12, n2, pp 67-79, doi 10.5335/rbca.v12i2.10531, issn = 2176-6649.
- [9] Lemen, J.R., Title, A.M., Akin, D. J., Boerner, P.F. et al., 2011, "The Atmospheric Imaging Assembly (AIA) on the Solar Dynamics Observatory (SDO)", The Solar Dynamics Observatory}, Springer US}, New York, NY, v9781461436, pp17-40, doi 10.1007/978-1-4614-3673-7_3, isbn 9781461436737.

CONTACT INFORMATION

André Leon Sampaio Gradvohl
gradvohl@unicamp.br